

the fertility change of Zhenong 1S. This indicates that the change from sterility to fertility for Zhenong 1S is stable and clear under field conditions in Hangzhou (35° 05' N).

The sterility of W6154S, which is being widely used for two-line hybrid

rices in China, is primarily controlled by higher temperature (29.7 °C) and not by longer photoperiod (Table 2). Therefore it has limited use in hybrid seed production.

The self-sterility rate of Zhenong 1S under long photoperiod (14.75 h) is above 99.7%, regardless of temperature. Under

short photoperiod (13.25 h), the self-seed setting rate of Zhenong 1S increases as temperature falls. This confirms that under long photoperiod, Zhenong 1S is completely sterile, but fertility is induced under short photoperiod (13.25 h) with lower temperature (25.7 °C). ■

Evaluation of male sterile lines with Honglien cytosterility

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A 4 × 4 incomplete diallel cross involving four male sterile lines of Honglien-type Cong-Guang 41 A, Zhao-Tai A, Qing-Lu A, and Qing-Er A, and restorer lines Te-Qing 2, Qi-Ja-Zhan, Zhen-Gui-Ai, and Qing-Lu-Ai was carried out in 1990 to study the combining ability of the male sterile lines and their biological properties.

We planted the 16 hybrids in a randomized block design with three replications in the early season (from Mar

to Jul 1991) under irrigated conditions. Sixty seedlings were transplanted at 16.7 × 20-cm spacing in each plot.

Cong-Guang 41 A was a good general combiner for plant height, individual plant yield, 1,000-grain weight, total spikelets per panicle, number of full grains per panicle, and seed set percentage, but not for number of effective panicles per hill (Table 1).

Qing-Er A was a poor combiner for seed set percentage, suggesting that it was not easily restored.

Cong-Guang 41 A was tallest; Qing-Er A was shortest. Cong-Guang 41 A had large panicles and few spikelets enclosed in the leaf sheath. Qing-Er A was high in stigma exsertion rate, followed by Cong-Guang 41 A (Table 2).

Cong-Guang 41 A appears to be a superior male sterile line compared with the other lines. ■

L-proline-mediated, high-frequency regeneration in rice cultivar IR66

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We initiated calli cultures from seeds of rice cultivar IR66. The dehulled seeds were washed with distilled water and then surface-sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for 5 min. Seeds were washed three times with sterile distilled water and placed in 150-ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing 30 ml of solid medium. The culture medium for calli induction consisted of basal Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with 2,4-D (2 mg/liter), coconut water (10%, vol/vol), and sucrose (3%, wt/vol). The cultures were incubated at 26 ± 2 °C under continuous light of about 2,000 lx. The calli obtained were subcultured on calli induction medium at an interval of 21 d.

After two subcultures, calli were transferred to medium that had L-proline incorporated into it at 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, and 1.0 mg/liter and incubated for 21 d. The proline-treated calli were then transferred to regeneration medium composed of basal MS salts supplemented with IAA (1.0 mg/liter) and BAP (0.3 mg/liter).

Green spots appeared in the calli while being incubated for 21 d. The spots developed slowly and there were not as many in the calli not treated with proline. We transferred the spots to either solid or liquid medium having the

Table 1. General combining ability effects of the male sterile lines. Guangdong, China, 1991.

Male sterile line	General combining ability (%)						
	Plant ht	Individual plant yield	1000-grain wt	Total spikelets/panicle	Full grains/panicle	Seed set	Effective panicles/hill
Qing-Lu A	2.46	6.21	0.50	-3.68	-3.73	1.92	4.73
Qing-Er A	-8.42	-17.10	-4.63	-9.34	-16.58	-6.78	4.62
Zhao-Tai A	2.31	1.54	2.14	-0.83	0.61	0.72	-1.98
Cong-Guang 41 A	3.64	9.26	1.94	13.84	19.67	4.14	-9.01
LSD (P = 0.05)	4.51	0.99	1.28	11.98	11.70	5.33	1.88

Table 2. Agronomic characters of the male sterile lines. Guangdong, China, 1991.

Male sterile line	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Length (cm) of panicles enclosed in leaf sheath	Spikelets enclosed/panicle (no.)	Leaves/main culm (no.)	Stigma exsertion rate (%)
Qing-Lu A	85.3	10.3	148.0	4.56	3.8	15.11	23.47
Qing-Er A	69.0	9.0	128.2	4.61	4.0	15.54	65.38
Zhao-Tai A	84.0	10.0	117.8	5.09	5.1	14.50	32.16
Cong-Guang 41 A	93.0	7.3	210.5	5.26	1.9	15.00	43.16
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.34	2.4	13.6	ns ^a	2.3	0.78	8.56

^aNonsignificant.